

Hello and welcome to the first LNL newsletter edited by me, David Smailes, as part of my role as Chair of the Local Network Leads.

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LNL News and Spotlight

Are you interested in game-based approaches to learning about Open Research Practices? If so, please email me (david.smailes@northumbria.ac.uk), as we plan to develop a working group/special interest group about this. You can find more context about this if you watch the recording of February's LNL Meeting (click on [this link](#)), where we started a discussion on this topic.

In a bit of a change from previous editions of this Newsletter, our 'Spotlight' section will now involve me sharing a recent talk from one of our LNLs. Hopefully, this will allow us all to get to know their work/their background a little better. First up, if you follow [this link](#), you'll be able to watch a talk given by Nadia Soliman (Imperial College London) on leadership and research culture.

Funding/Job Opportunities

Gustav Nilsson at the Karolinska Institutet is inviting postdoctoral candidates to develop joint proposals for postdoc positions in metascience. More information is available [here](#).

My own institution (Northumbria Uni) are advertising a Research Fellow in Implementation Science post. The post isn't explicitly about open research/metascience, but would involve working with Sebastian Pothoff, who is Director of [Open Digital Health](#). More information is available [here](#).

Welcomes and Goodbyes

Please welcome new LNLs joining UKRN, and thank you to those stepping out of the role to move onto other exciting opportunities! We try to report all changes but if we miss you, please let us know and we will include you in the next newsletter.

Please welcome the new LNL for Leicester - Michael Biddle (find out more about Michael at [this link](#)).

Huge thanks, goodbye, and good luck to previous LNL at Leicester, Sarah Gunn.

We are currently looking for new LNLs within University of Exeter, University of Gloucestershire, and University of Greenwich. If you have relevant contacts there please let us know so we can follow up - contact@ukrn.org

LNL Past Events - Now Resources for You

The recent LNL webinar ‘Transparency and Openness Promotion (TOP) Guidelines’ given by Suzanne Stewart is now available [here](#). In this presentation Suzanne explains what the TOP guidelines are, why and how they have been updated, and how you can use the TOP guidelines in both your own research and your work as an LNL.

UKRN Resources

There's a really good post on the UKRN website from Dr Reny Baykova (School of Psychology, University of Sussex) about a project where an independent statistician (Reny) checks and certifies the computational reproducibility of papers before they are submitted for publication. Read the post [here](#).

External Conferences & Other Events

Between the 24th and 27th of February, University of Liverpool, Liverpool John Moore's University, Edge Hill University and University of Essex are running free online sessions (which are open to all) as part of their Open Research Week. Find more information [here](#).

The Freiburg Open Science Mini-Conference is running on May 15th and 16th. registration is free and they are currently accepting abstract submissions to present at one of their poster sessions. Find more information [here](#).

Reading Recommendations

Nature Methods have just published an editorial on 'Reporting methods for reusability'. You can find it [here](#).

And an interesting pre-print from Sajedeh Rasti, Krist Vaesen, and Daniel Lakens that introduces a framework describing different levels of scientific co-ordination can be found [here](#).

Closing Remarks

If you would like to contribute, or have something that you think should be shared (especially for the Spotlight section!), please get in touch. We would love to hear from you; it's your newsletter! contact@ukrn.org
